

Advancing SDG 4: Enhancing Financial Literacy through Interactive Learning Methods in Accounting Education

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This study examines how interactive teaching methods affect accounting students' financial literacy in institutions of higher learning and the contribute to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal 4: Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all". Using a PRISMA systematic literature review, the study examines the literature from published peer-reviewed articles extracted from Scopus and Google Scholar databases. The study findings reveal that innovative and interactive learning methods make a positive impact on the financial acumen and academic performance of accounting students in South African institutions of higher learning. The originality of this study consists of conceptualising the interactive learning methods for financial literacy and equitable quality (ILMFLEQ) framework, as it illustrates in a systematic manner how interactive learning methods link to financial literacy and equitable quality education in accounting regarding specific relevance to both the South African higher education context and SDG 4. The practical implication of the study is that collective policy execution at Higher Education Institutions, professional accounting bodies and the government level is crucial to standardise assessment practices to accommodate and support interactive pedagogies and fund sustainable strategic digital transformation initiatives to ensure equitable, quality learning outcomes for all accounting students. The evidence of interactive learning methods is limited to a systematic literature review and different conclusions could be reached by collecting empirical data from accounting learners and instructors.

Keywords: Interactive learning methods, financial literacy, accounting students, higher education institutions

In recent years, the accounting profession worldwide has immensely changed with the influence of technology and the evolving needs of the business community. This has necessitated a reconfiguration of conventional teaching methods of accountancy to enhance financial literacy for university students in a developing country such as South Africa (Makhathini & Akpa-Inyang, 2024). It is contended that innovative accounting education, which entails interactive learning approaches, is significant in mitigating the challenges confronting accounting graduates as they practice in an ever-evolving digital environment (Sebele-Mpofu, 2024). It has also been contended that contemporary educational approaches, including interactive learning, are effective strategies to facilitate students' comprehension and application of financial principles (Sithole & Abeysekera, 2021). This research focuses on the impact of interactive learning methods on the financial literacy of students in Higher Education Institutions.

In the South African university environment, innovative methods of teaching accounting have gained greater recognition (Viviers &

de Villiers, 2020). For instance, previous research indicates that Information and Communication Technology (ICTs) not only enhance the presentation of accounting information but also build skills that can be readily transferred to real financial management (Ahmad & Sheikh, 2022). This shift is also supported by data from the COVID-19 Pandemic which illustrates that the move towards online and blended learning settings, although imperfect, has prompted innovative learning methodologies that have the potential to build stronger financial literacy (Asad et al., 2022).

The necessity of graduates to become financially literate has been noted in various research studies (Kuntze et al., 2019; Muniarty et al., 2025; Abanum et al., 2025). For instance, in their systematic review, Kuntze et al. (2029) pointed out that modern ICTs which should be incorporated into pedagogies improves financial literacy scores of business students. Moreover, new technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI), data analytics, and blockchain are transforming the accountancy profession and improving financial literacy among students (Muniarty et al., 2025). Thus, students can make wiser financial decisions (Muniarty et al., 2025).

The study adds to the literature by identifying how different interactive learning methodologies are effective in diverse cultural backgrounds. It also illustrates how educational techniques can be adapted to the needs of university students in a better way. It emphasises financial literacy by highlighting the importance of providing quality and inclusive accounting education to students at universities in order to equip them with sufficient financial management skills that are of vital importance for personal and professional development. Based on its results, this study offers highly valued recommendations to educators seeking to create a better learning environment for their students and enhance financial literacy within Higher Education Institutions.

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The goal of the paper is to analyse selected examples of innovative accounting education approaches deployed across higher learning institutions by identifying best practices and common challenges through a systematic review approach. For this purpose, an intensive literature review has been carried out on the literature regarding the development of financial literacy through interactive learning methods. By offering insights into the impact of interactive learning methods on financial literacy, this research seeks to contribute to ongoing debates about educational innovation in higher education in support of SDG 4: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all”, and to eventually help to shape practices and policies that will relate to accounting education. Moreover, by gaining insight into how interactive learning methods affect financial literacy, this research strives to add to the current debate about educational innovation within higher education in support of SDG 4, and eventually help to shape practices and policies that are related to accounting education.

In the present study, an innovative teaching model in accounting education based on interactive learning methods has been proposed, and the following research questions have been presented:

Research Questions

- *Q1*: How effective are interactive learning methods in improving financial literacy among accounting students?
- *Q2*: How do interactive learning methods in accounting education contribute to inclusive and equitable learning experiences?

Section two discusses the theoretical foundations and the methodology is presented in section three. Section four analyses the study findings, and finally the conclusions are presented in section five.

Theoretical Foundations

Constructivist Learning Theory

According to Bada and Olusegun (2015), under the Constructivist Learning Theory, learners develop knowledge actively through reflection and experience rather than passively. The theory identifies the importance of innovative methods of learning that enhance the ways of understanding and retaining the concepts of accounting, thereby improving the financial literacy of learners. Lin et al. (2024) contend that the fundamental principle of constructivism entails the active involvement of learners in an interactive engagement with the subject matter, a process that facilitates the development of more

profound and comprehensive understandings of scholarly concepts.

With knowledge that students possess different learning styles, interactive methods can be flexible to accommodate all learning styles including visual, auditory, and kinesthetic (Emma, 2024). It is with such flexibility that a diversity-friendly learning environment is created (Omoseebi et al., 2024). These methods play a basic role in enhancing financial literacy among diverse groups (Harianto et al., 2024). In summary, the Constructivist Learning Theory provides a very engaging platform through which to develop improved financial literacy by way of creative accounting instruction combined with active participation. Accounting instructors can greatly enhance students' understanding and application of accounting concepts by emphasising interactive learning as well as tailor-making specific educational experiences to match their socio-economic backgrounds. This eventually enables students to sustainably manage their financial futures.

Sustainable Development Goal 4: Quality Education

The aim of SDG 4 is to promote social justice and equality through inclusive and equitable quality education. SDG 4 recognises the significance of education for sustained development, economic prosperity, and social equity (Saini et al., 2023). The key objectives of SDG 4 include numeracy for youth and universal literacy and a substantial proportion of the adult population, as well as equipping all learners with the competencies and understanding that are crucial for contributing to sustainable development (Hanemann, 2019). In South African Higher Education Institutions, attaining a high-quality education is of paramount importance in line with SDG 4. South Africa confronts distinctive economic challenges necessitating a financially literate populace to foster sustainable national growth (Shava, 2020). Equitable and inclusive learning environments can be further facilitated by interactive pedagogical approaches, which can easily address diverse student learning needs that emanate from different socioeconomic backgrounds (Memon & Memon, 2025). Secondly, the integration of interactive pedagogical approaches into accounting education is key to ensuring that the SDG goals are met, hence enhancing financial literacy among students. Thus, through the use of engaging and collaborative pedagogical approaches, lecturers within South African Higher Education Institutions can empower students with skills in the management of financial matters (Nyagope, 2024; Mpofu & Chasokela, 2025). Table 1 briefly outlines the targets of SDG 4.

Table 1
SDG 4 Quality Education

Goal	Targets
Ensure access to quality inclusive education and learning opportunities for all	1. Provide universal primary and secondary education
	2. Early childhood development and pre-primary education for all
	3. Equal success in higher education and technical/vocational programs for all
	4. Useful skills for decent work
	5. Inclusion and Gender Equality
	6. Youth literacy for all
	7. Education for Global Citizenship and Sustainable Development

Note. Source: United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (2015)

Method

Research Design

This investigation is guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) protocol. This study endeavours to synthesise extant literature concerning interactive learning methodologies within accounting education and their impact on enhancing financial literacy, supporting the achievement of SDG4. Similar studies have used the PRISMA methodology, which includes (López-Sánchez, Patiño-Vanegas, Valencia-Arias, & Valencia, 2023; & Juniardi & Putra, 2024).

Data Sources and Search Strategies

The study presented research questions as guided by the Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome approach, with searches conducted in Scopus and Google Scholar databases. The study used keywords and Boolean operators such as financial literacy, accounting education, blended learning, interactive learning, active learning, gamification, online learning, simulation, technology-enhanced learning, SDG 4, sustainable development goal 4, and quality education. Boolean operators “AND”, “OR”, were used to link keywords such as innovative learning methods, interactive learning methods, university, higher education, quality education, equity, innovation, SDG 4, inclusive learning, financial literacy, and accounting students, in search of relevant articles in the Scopus database.

The search strategies were structured as follows:

In Scopus: (“financial literacy” OR “financial management” OR “investment education” OR “financial planning” OR “accounting principles”) AND (“accounting education”) AND (“interactive learning” OR “active learning” OR “technology-enhanced learning” OR “simulation” OR “gamification” OR “case-based learning” OR “collaborative learning” OR “problem-based learning” OR “think-pair-share” OR “discussions” OR “e-learning” OR “online learning” OR “buss session”) AND (“SDG 4” OR “sustainable development goal 4” OR “quality education” OR “education for sustainable development”) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , “BUSI”) OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , “ECON”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, “ar”)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, “English”).

In Google Scholar: “financial literacy” AND “accounting education” “high school” “secondary education” AND (“interactive learning” OR “active learning” OR “technology-enhanced learning” OR “gamification” OR “simulation” OR “case-based learning” AND “SDG4” OR “sustainable development goal 4” OR “quality education”)

Inclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria targeted studies that were published from 2020 to 2025, written in English, subjected to peer review and had a focus on university-level education. The studies were included as long as they focused on accounting education at the tertiary institutions level, looked at interactive learning methods, reported outcomes on financial literacy or quality education, or inclusive education (SDG 4). The period 2020 to 2025 was considered in this study because the majority of countries and institutions began implementing education reforms and e-learning strategies around 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which accelerated learning modality innovation (Tilak & Kumar, 2022). The period saw more and more widespread use of

online, blended, and interactive pedagogies, thus making the period rich for evaluating their influence (Singh, Steele, & Singh, 2021). Some of the countries' accrediting agencies and education policies revised their standards from 2020 to 2025 to incorporate competency-based education, digital literacy, and sustainability issues (Laskar, 2024; Anapey, 2025).

Exclusion Criteria

The excluded documents relate to conference proceedings, editorials, book chapters, reviews, reports, commentary pieces, editorials, articles not written in English, and studies irrelevant to the business, management, and accounting disciplines. Conference proceedings and reviews do not go through the same level of peer review as regular manuscripts and as such, do not present empirical results; neither does their detailed methodology offer enough for a PRISMA-guided systematic review; therefore, they have been removed from this review (Singh et al., 2021; Marzi et al., 2025). Furthermore, the peer-review standards of book chapters vary significantly between publishers (Dagienè, 2023).

The Screening Process

The process of selecting relevant documents followed the PRISMA flow. Following the search query, documents were filtered using the publication period from 2020 to 2025, accounting for the subject area and the English language. Results of the identified documents from the advanced search query were exported to the CSV Excel file. The Excel file was used to sort out the documents by author and title, and duplicate files were deleted. This process was followed by the screening of abstracts, and each record was marked as either include = 1, exclude = 0, or maybe = 2. Full documents with abstracts marked as 'include' or 'maybe' were downloaded and the researchers read the abstracts to confirm the eligibility or exclusion criteria again. Articles with abstracts not related to the research questions were excluded from the final analysis. The PRISMA diagram in Figure 1 below documents the review process.

Figure 1

PRISMA Review Process; Page, McKenzie, Bossuyt, Boutron, Hoffmann, Mulrow, Shamseer, Tetzlaff, Akl, Brennan, & Chou, 2021.

Data Extraction and Analysis

The data were extracted onto a standardised form that captured author(s), year, country, study design, interactive learning method applied, financial literacy outcomes, and contribution to SDG 4. Content analysis was conducted by identifying themes that highlighted effective strategies and gaps in current practice.

Quality Assessment

The rigour and quality of the methods employed in studies selected for analysis were verified using a standard checklist. Items included clarity of research questions, appropriateness of the study design, sample representativeness, and strength of findings.

Data Synthesis

Data were synthesised qualitatively by focusing on the identification of common themes and effective interactive learning methods. A narrative synthesis was carried out in order to summarise findings and indicate implications for accounting education and the enhancement of financial literacy and quality education.

Results

This section analyses the study findings derived from the PRISMA-based systematic literature review focusing on advancing SDG 4 (Quality Education) through enhanced financial literacy, using interactive learning methods in accounting education. It synthesises evidence from peer-reviewed studies to identify prevailing trends, pedagogical innovations and gaps in current practices.

Demographic Information

Figure 2

Documents by Year

Note. Source: own work

Figure 2 reveals a gradual increase in research output from 2020 to 2024 with respect to the contribution of interactive learning methods in accounting and financial literacy on SDG 4. The COVID-19 effects resulted in a drop in research publications in 2021. After 2023, the publication of research articles increased. This can be attributed to the call to align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals by 2030.

The distribution of publications by country is shown in Figure 3. The search from the Scopus and Google Scholar databases resulted in South Africa being identified as the country with the highest publications analysed in this study. Australia and the United Kingdom also contributed a significant number of research articles analysed in the study. India, France, Costa Rica, and Canada all

contributed the least number of articles analysed in the study. Overall, the analysis relates to both the South African and the International contexts.

Figure 3

Documents by Country

Note. Source: own work

Figure 4

Documents by Type

Note. Source: own work

All the documents downloaded and analysed in this study include research articles published in peer-reviewed journals, as presented in Figure 4. Conference papers, book chapters, reviews, and reports were excluded from this study. The reason being that research articles are subjected to rigorous reviews which ensure the credibility of the work done by researchers.

Figure 5

Documents by Subject Area

Note. Source: own work

Figure 5 shows that all research articles downloaded and analysed

address the use of interactive learning methods for teaching business, management, and accounting students at institutions of higher learning. Publications in other disciplines for example, computer sciences, environmental studies, and social sciences, were excluded as they lacked relevance to the research topic and objectives.

Content Analysis

- The role of interactive learning methods in improving financial literacy among accounting students

Simulation-based Experiential Learning: The students' satisfaction level and understanding of practical applications in finance can be improved by Simulation-based experiential learning activities (Bakoush, 2022). In this respect, financial competency and literacy have been enhanced through the creation and usage of high-quality digital tools, becoming more efficient-especially at enhancing positive financial behaviour and appropriate decision-making (Mori, 2021). Bakoush (2022) found that students' understanding of finance theories and concepts improve when they are motivated to implement deep learning strategies due to higher satisfaction levels. Accounting software simulation, for example, allows students to gain experience with industry-standard tools and it addresses the limitations of academic learning by practical applications (Sonjaya et al., 2024). Students also believe that practical experience, which they engage with enhances their employability (Bakoush, 2022). Simulations realistically imitate practical accounting and decision-making processes, thus supporting students to acquire their skills in a no-risk environment (Sonjaya et al., 2024).

Project-based Learning: In higher education the evidence show that project-based learning promotes knowledge, skills, and motivation within collaborative and interdisciplinary settings (Larsen, 2025). The results of the literature review highlight how project-based learning can help solve the lack of competency skills faced by many graduates when seeking employment (Larsen, 2025). The literature review found that, by implementing the project-based learning approach, the financial literacy of students improved significantly (Lin, 2025). Apart from the pedagogical value, project-based learning offers a special opportunity to link academic teaching to challenges from the real world for the benefit of students, instructors, and external partners. Thus, project-based learning method integrates theoretical knowledge with practical application through idea development, discussion, and the sharing of opinions (Lin, 2025).

Case-based Learning: Sonjaya et al. (2024) argue that case-based learning method bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application (Sonjaya et al., 2024). As highlighted by Sonjaya et al. (2024), the case study encourages applying theoretical knowledge to practice, enhancing critical thinking and decision-making skills by relating students to real-world situations. Students, through participation in a realistic business scenario, enhance their ability to critically analyse financial data and make strategic decisions in a well-informed manner (Sonjaya et al., 2024). Theoretical ideas are connected with practical implementation and help students appreciate how their academic knowledge applies in reality (Sonjaya et al., 2024). A study conducted by Tran and Herzig (2023) establish that the use of an integrated case-based teaching methodology improves critical thinking, communication skills, and collaboration.

Problem-based Learning: Problem-based learning is also

acknowledged to engender higher-order cognitive abilities. Problem-based learning encourages independent learning and critical thinking, aspects which are very important to accountants nowadays in their dealings with increasingly complex and ambiguous situations within a business context (Sonjaya et al., 2024). By working through complex real-life problems, students develop critical and creative thinking, thus coming up with strategies that demand a deeper understanding of accounting concepts and methods (Sonjaya et al., 2024). Active problem-based learning engagement enhances understanding of the problem, reduces the expectation of further explanation, and, also, reduces time devoted to individual learning (Lee, 2025). According to Ahmed and Kannaiah (2018), accounting students develop communication, teamwork, leadership, and presentation competencies among others through the implementation of problem-based learning approaches.

Blended Learning: Blended learning is adaptable to different learning preferences and contexts, making it a realistic approach to contemporary accounting education (Sonjaya et al., 2024). In this case, students would be able to access material and collaborate with peers remotely while getting direct interaction from instructors in class (Sonjaya et al., 2024). Taking into consideration the e-learning environment, Russo et al. (2022) noticed that accounting students perceived this virtual approach as one having greater potential for improving the learning experience. Evidence shows the potential of a blended learning model as an effective instructional design for promoting the development of transferable skills in technical programs (Russo et al., 2022).

Flipped Classroom: The use of information technology has allowed the flipped classroom to grant students with access to resources for study such as video tutorials which learners can easily access, view, and learn from in advance (Kottara, 2025). For accounting education, students would be able to watch videos during their tailored timetable and review lectures and materials outside the classroom (Sonjaya et al., 2024). Subsequently, class time could be used for discussion, problem-solving, and group projects. This means that the retention scores of Business Education students who receive instruction in Financial Accounting through a flipped classroom approach are higher than those taught through the use of a traditional method (Bupo & Ibenem, 2022). This is because the flipped classroom approach, utilising a Learning Management System (LMS) encourages self-directed learning, increases student engagement, and is more student-centered when compared to the traditional face-to-face teaching (Bupo & Ibenem, 2022). With the implementation of the flipped classroom model, accounting educators take up the role of lesson designers and develop proper educational material using effective digital tools (Kottara, 2025).

- The contribution of interactive learning methods in accounting education to SDG 4

The use of interactive seminars, group work, and project work provided a rich educational experience for students, allowing them to acquire a deep understanding of theoretical knowledge related to sustainability in practice as well as applying it in their day-to-day lives (Maharani et al., 2025). By promoting financial education, students are assisted in their transition to the world of work, which can be seen as a driving force in getting rid of inequality and developing in a sustainable manner (Mori, 2021). This also appears not to be a surprise in that a sound financial status is being a direct step in escaping the plight of poverty and further contribute to sustainable development whereas financial literacy has been

increasingly accepted as a basic life skill for the 21st century (Mori, 2021). This would help students in providing insights, pointing out that university knowledge gained would help in overcoming practical problems faced in adopting SDGs (Kottara et al., 2025). The knowledge of students in technology, along with effective and quick access to information without using printed articles that cause environmental pollution, would help in all ways in e-learning. A meaningful experience in the study would be received through blended learning, along with advancements in green learning management systems such as Moodle for digitizing (Kottara et al., 2025). There would be immense benefits in economic, societal, as well as environmental ways, which are all in support of achieving quality education and in promoting lifelong learning, reinforcing SDG 4 (Kottara et al., 2025).

Accounting education using blended learning approaches, particularly in modules such as financial accounting, encourages practices that ensure exclusive, meaningful, and sustainable learning experiences (Kottara et al., 2025). Digital transformation is inherently about improving many facets of education, including improving the quality of instruction and improving institutional efficiency as well as expand access to quality education in communities that have been marginalised (Al-Maaitah et al., 2025). Digital tools integrated into sustainable accounting education can enable inclusiveness, scalability, and effectiveness in learning (Al-Maaitah et al., 2025). Technologies integrated into learning environments offer the ability to widen access to quality education, reducing costs, improving efficiency, and improving learner engagement, thus contributing towards a more adaptable and inclusive education system (Al-Maaitah et al., 2025). In this sense, it is fundamental for the growth of the profession and future survival for accounting professionals that training be provided for individuals who can adapt to the digital transformation age (Tavares et al., 2023). To this effect, all entities involved in the profession at large, including educational institutions, companies, professional associations, regulatory bodies, and the government, need to offer accounting education that aligns with the industry demands for new skills by creating synergies that promote and support human capital for acquiring and developing the competencies needed for this ever-evolving digital age (Tavares et al., 2023).

- The South African context

The use of interactive learning methods in South Africa's Higher Education Institutions play an important role in promoting financial literacy for accounting students through active engagement, collaboration, and practical application of concepts. The findings by Ngwenya and Arek-Bawa (2022) highlight that students acquire the necessary analytical and problem-solving skills in accounting to assess and understand financial information through group work, hence promoting accountability, interdependence, and social interaction. To that effect, Seleke (2024) points out that interactive learning methods include online simulations and blended learning in which responsive and adaptive learning environments enhance participation and responsibility, thus enabling the bridging of the distance and accommodating individualised learning. Such approaches, therefore, support constructivist theory in which students construct knowledge by engaging themselves with such experiences. In addition, integrating ICT-enhanced methods into the curriculum boost the chances of getting employed and equips them with essential skills, promotes digital inclusion as well as overcome regulatory challenges in South Africa (Mpanza, 2025).

Interactive learning approaches play a significant role in accounting education and contribute to meeting the inclusive and equity-based targets of SDG 4 by ensuring that more student-centered learning methods support diverse needs of learning for students with various socio-economic backgrounds. Constructivist learning methodologies such as collaboration, reflection, and dynamic assessment practices improve engagement for an untapped student mass, including those with marginal backgrounds, by establishing a clear connection between new learning and existing experiences, promoting a sense of inclusivity (Musundwa, 2025). Moreover, innovative learning methods that establish connections between theoretical principles and applications through technology-based solutions ensure that students from various backgrounds enjoy inclusive learning environments that ensure active learning, critical thinking, and collaboration with reduced disparities in learning achievements (Makhathini & Akpa-Inyang, 2024). Similarly, recent trends that incorporate e-learning solutions for more effective learning for students before, during, and after the pandemic have revealed that technology-based solutions promise opportunities for more effective learning, yet challenges related to equity and accessibility must be dealt with by overcoming issues like internet connections for more inclusive studying (Papageorgiou et al., 2024). Thus, interactive learning approaches, in total, align with meeting the objectives of SDG 4 by ensuring that accounting education practices are more inclusive, equitable, and responsive in South African institutions.

Notwithstanding the pervasive use of technology in accounting education, there are still various obstacles to overcome if the aim of ensuring that accounting students in South Africa receive inclusive, equitable, and quality education is to be met (Ade-Ibijola et al., 2025). The first challenge is that the Accounting professional bodies in South Africa prescribe the accounting curriculum, and the instructor's main focus is covering the syllabus comprehensively, a process that is often time-consuming yet very necessary to help the students to thoroughly prepare for the ITC and APC examinations (Dowelani & Dowelani, 2020; Ade-Ibijola et al., 2025). The syllabus comprises a voluminous scope of rule-based learning with a copious amount of complicated theoretical notions, guidelines, and statutes entailed in accounting, audit, taxation, and management accounting, thus restricting educators from applying innovative teaching methods in the classrooms (Ade-Ibijola et al., 2025). The findings from the literature review reveal that involving practice work through case studies or simulation learning is a prudent approach to compensate for the drawbacks of Work-Integrated Learning (WIL) program which at times defer graduation in case of non-accessibility to placements (Makhathini & Akpa-Inyang, 2024). It is extremely essential to integrate strategic thinking, Fourth Industrial Revolution, within the syllabus (Makhathini & Akpa-Inyang, 2024). The inclusion of strategic thinking and incorporation of the Fourth Industrial Revolution principles into the curriculum is of critical importance (Makhathini & Akpa-Inyang, 2024). The existing frameworks, which mostly remain theoretical, need to develop with increased experiences with advancements in technologies to efficiently equip students with prudence, vigilance, and foresightedness within the changing premises of the accounting environment (Makhathini & Akpa-Inyang, 2024). Ade-Ibijola et al. (2025) recommend Zulu Augmented Reality Translation (ZART) development which will enhance the competence and position of South African chartered accountants and contribute to achieving SDG 4.

Discussion

Accounting education has seen an unprecedented level of change with innovative methods such as learning from multimedia text with videos linked in a spreadsheet using a QR code, playing a very effective role in filling the gap between theoretical knowledge and implementation (Saputra et al., 2025). Such approaches assist in developing students' skill sets and taking part in learning through self-directed learning and experiential learning (Saputra et al., 2025). In terms of financial literacy, technology-enabled educational programs in developing countries show immense potential in improving both learning and implementation in subjects related to financial education, especially devised in mobile apps and online learning portals offering scalable, personalised, and dynamic learning resources (Menberu, 2024). GeoGebra-introduced learning objects in accounting education have testified with conviction that dynamic illustrations of financial concepts, such as Gross Profit and Net Income have proved far more effective in improving students' mathematical skills and analysis capabilities for financial statements for making educated decisions to improve financial accuracy in governance and management (Gaviria-Rodríguez et al., 2024). On a similar note, the game learning approach utilising learning opportunities with some recommended board games such as "My Budget and My First Million" have proved very effective in developing students' implementable financial capabilities, suggesting good or excellent knowledge attainment levels, with understandable improvements in key skill sets including budgeting, savings, and protecting against financial fraud (Rebukha, Kizyma, & Pysmennyi, 2020). Such programs improve access to education among marginalised communities in addition to ensuring financial inclusion or permanent behavioral change, despite struggles in dealing with digital divides in technology acceptance.

Existing literature recognises that an innovative and interactive technological pedagogical application positively impacts the financial acumen and academic performance of accounting students in South Africa's tertiary institutions. As stated in a literature analysis by Seleke (2024) an ICT-enabled strategy, with blended learning designs and incorporating learning management systems, multimedia educational content, and accounting software, remains more conducive to student-centric learning in terms of developing engagement, autonomous learning, and application of theoretical principles to a practical context despite infrastructural weaknesses in a rural environment. Similarly, Makhathini and Akpa-Inyang (2024) show how the integration of case studies, simulations, and modules from other disciplines within a financial accounting course, relating the theoretical aspect to practical exposure, develops critical thinking skills, and aligns what is learned in universities with what is expected at work while identifying the need for continuous professional development by faculty members. As such, this research collectively buttresses the fact that an interactive learning approach, including information and communication technology integration, experiential learning, and curriculum restructuring, becomes imperative in developing financial literacy, promoting student engagement, and preparing graduates for the evolving demands of the accounting profession in South Africa.

Interactive learning approaches such as projects, internship, case studies, and learning through collaborations are greatly relevant in ensuring a learning environment in accounting education where students have equal opportunities. For instance, experiential learning methodologies such as case studies and sustainability reports analysis allow students to connect theoretical concepts with real-world problems, thus, developing critical thinking and problem-solving capabilities necessary for dealing with sustainability issues in accounting practice (Latifah & Ivada, 2025). Project learning and internship programs provide authentic settings where students can apply technical, social, and ethical perspectives of accounting, thus overcoming challenges faced by students in case they have difficulty in learning using traditional lecture methods (Othman & Ameer, 2024). Collaborative learning settings, such as group work and projects, promote inclusiveness in learning by appreciating differences and working together. This is a critical step in equipping accounting students with the capacity to work in a multicultural and interdisciplinary environment (Al-Hazaima et al., 2025). García and De los Ríos (2021) support such an approach in their study by pointing out that learning methods such as project learning, internship, or business simulations can help students in applying theoretical principles into practice, thus developing their skills in accounting in accordance with Industry 4.0 and Agenda 2030 standards. Such learning methods focus on developing teamwork, critical thinking, and resilience, which are important traits in dealing with complexities in the accounting profession.

Implications for South African Higher Education

The findings stress the need to move away from content-driven accounting curricula with a rule-based focus towards interactive, constructivist pedagogical methods that develop high-order competencies and real-life financial skills. Given the fast-track nature and high content coverage of SAICA examination preparation, ring-fenced curriculum time should be afforded to simulation-based experiential learning, case-based and problem-based learning, project-based assignments, and blended or flipped learning methods. To ensure inclusivity in line with Sustainable Development Goal 4, universities must invest in digital equity infrastructure (for example, low-data content, device loan programmes, campus Wi-Fi) and multilingual, interactive tools such as augmented reality/artificial intelligence-enabled isiZulu resources and communities of practice to build lecturer capacity.

Simulations and case studies help alleviate work-integrated learning placement requirements and boost experiential learning. Higher education courses need to incorporate financial literacy by infusing gamification strategies, comprehensive learning modules, and microlearning features to enhance the skills of students on budgeting, saving, debt management, and fraud prevention. The incorporation of these elements clearly contributes towards increasing employability and overall well-being among students. Collective policy execution at institutions, SAICA, professional bodies and the government level is crucial to standardise assessment practices to accommodate and support interactive pedagogies and fund sustainable strategic digital transformation initiatives to ensure equitable, quality learning outcomes for all accounting students.

● Alignment with Constructivist Learning Theory and SDG 4

Findings	Constructivist principle	SDG4 target contribution
PjBL improves knowledge, skills, motivation, and bridges workforce competency gaps	Learners build understanding through authentic projects; prior knowledge & transfer emphasized	4.4 (skills for employment), 4.7 (education for sustainable development)
Case-/Problem-based learning enhances higher-order skills, critical thinking, teamwork	Social interaction, collaboration, and inquiry drive knowledge construction	4.1 (quality learning outcomes), 4.5 (equity), 4.7 (global citizenship & sustainability)
Blended & flipped learning increase autonomy, engagement, access	Self-regulation, scaffolded exploration, multiple pathways to learn	4.3 (equal access to tertiary education), 4.a (education facilities & technology)
Multilingual tools (ZART) widen access and Comprehension	Connecting new knowledge to lived experience and language	4.5 (eliminate gender & socio-economic disparities), 4.6 (literacy & numeracy)
Simulations/games & GeoGebra ILOs build practical financial behaviours & statement literacy	Experiential, iterative refinement via feedback	4.6 (financial literacy as functional literacy), 4.4 (technical skills)

Note. Source: own work

Figure 6

The Interactive Learning Methods for Financial Literacy and Equitable Quality (ILMFLED)

Note. Source: own compilation

Figure 6 above shows the proposed conceptual framework (ILMFLEQ) that guides the incorporation of interactive learning methods in accounting education. The application process begins with the support factors that form the core structure, including alignment, digital equity infrastructure, and capacity development. They provide a basis for implementation of the Pedagogical Core that focuses on constructivist approaches such as authentic learning outcomes, collaborative learning, and autonomy. Further, instruction delivery is enabled through technology-enhanced learning approaches such as integrated learning, simulations, and support for multiple languages. Two main learning outcomes are offered in this conceptual model: improvement in financial acumen and accounting knowledge. Lastly, this conceptual model aims to achieve equity and supports a constant improvement loop via a feedback system that enforces a change in policies and infrastructure, thereby aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 4.

Conclusion

This study confirms that interactive methods of instruction such as simulations, project learning, case studies, blended learning, or flexible classrooms can significantly enhance financial literacy

skills and accounting skills among students in higher education institutions. These methods of instruction enable active participation, collaboration, and application of concepts, hence enriching theoretical foundations of instruction through hands-on learning. By embracing technological-based strategies, universities can ensure a synergy between accounting education and the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal 4. However, the challenges faced in the implementation within the South African university set-up are uneven, and these are linked to systemic issues arising from the curriculum rigidity, digital inequalities, among other factors. Overcoming the challenges requires institutional commitment to improvement.

To further this agenda, future research must aim to empirically validate the new ILMFLEQ framework through longitudinal research and testing. Research on what works on a large scale in terms of digital equity strategies, including low-data computing systems and device loan projects is necessary to close the access gap. Future research must focus on culturally relevant variants of interactive methods, making multilingual support through the use of Augmented Reality and Artificial Intelligence translation tools. Comparative research on a regional basis will help uncover what

strategies work best in the implementation of new technologies such as blockchain, Virtual Reality, and Analytics into accounting education. Finally, scholarly research should focus on the development of equity dashboards for analysing sustainable, inclusive, and success rates within traditionally disadvantaged subgroups, along with evaluation for quality Faculty Development Frameworks for readiness for interactive methods.

The study made several contributions. To begin with, this research serves to extend the current literature on constructivist learning theory with the demonstration of the possible effective use of technology-integrated interactive learning methods in financial literacy and accounting education. Secondly, this research offers a conceptual framework (ILMFLEQ) that enables universities to include interactive learning methods into accounting education which would help universities in achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4. Thirdly, this research offers empirical information on the context of higher education in South Africa and the challenges as well as opportunities available for equitable learning. Finally, the research suggests that technology, such as ZART (Augmented Reality & AI Translation), might help make accounting education multilingual and culturally responsive.

Despite the above contributions, this paper has several limitations. These include that the evidence of interactive learning methods comes from the systematic literature review and their application in various learning institutions remains inconsistent. Furthermore, the use of interactive learning methods was not assessed longitudinally. While this study has pointed out certain technology-enhanced approaches, it did not consider issues of connectivity, availability, or literacy.

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